

Deriving Dark Phenomena and Gravity from Entropy Horizons

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Abstract

Contemporary physics has explanatory gaps in deriving cosmic acceleration and gravitational dynamics without assuming dark energy and matter [7]. This work explores an alternative perspective: modeling cosmic phenomena as emerging thermodynamically from quantum information loss across cosmic entropy horizons. Connections between horizon thermodynamics and black hole event horizons suggest information transfer into unobservable environmental degrees of freedom could induce subtle universal effects [9, 10].

Gradual decoherence between localized systems and vast cosmic Hilbert spaces over eons could lead to an extremely slow exponential scaling of mass-distance relationships [9, 10]. This emergent paradigm predicts unique signatures, such as modifications to gravitational lensing and galaxy rotation curves over cosmic history [10]. The framework motivates falsifiable tests distinguishable from contemporary cosmology.

Conceptually linking information theory to gravitational emergence dispenses with perplexing dark components. While theoretical challenges remain reconciling quantum and gravitational regimes, profound interconnections likely await discovery. This thermodynamic emergence paradigm inspires foundational inquiry into cosmic acceleration, gravitation, and spacetime emergence.

1 Introduction

Observations challenging standard cosmic models [1, 2, 3] apparently require perplexing dark energy and matter assumptions within general relativity [4, 5, 6]. However, their mysterious origins signal foundational omissions in contemporary physics [7, 8]. Our expansive universe remains filled with mystery.

Despite decades of astonishing progress in cosmology and physics, observational findings continue defying explanation within standard models, signaling gaps in contemporary theory. The perplexing notions of dark energy and matter now pervade cosmic paradigms, yet their metaphysical origins engender skepticism. Might our contemporary grasp still lack foundational pieces of the puzzle?

Seeking profound interconnections between quantum mechanics and general relativity has become physics' holy grail. In this pursuit, holographic entanglement and black hole thermodynamics have revealed deep links between information theory, entropy, and gravitational emergence [9, 10, 11, 12]. Could cosmic acceleration and gravitation emerge thermodynamically from quantum information loss across cosmic entropy horizons? In this intrinsically geometric view, horizons' enormous entropies [13, 14, 15] enable decoherence between localized systems and the environment over eons [16, 12], indirectly inducing subtle mass-distance scaling [9, 10]. Gravity itself arises holographically from quantum state entanglements across this entropy barrier. Dispensing with dark components, this thermodynamic emergence perspective offers ontological alternatives to contemporary cosmology.

By starting from ontological first principles, this approach renews intuitive connections between environmentally-induced decoherence and gravitational phenomena underpinning the hypothesis that cosmic acceleration, dark matter phenomena, dark energy and gravity emerge indirectly from intrinsic exponential quantum gravitational decay of all mass-energy $M(t)$ across cosmic time t described by:

$$M(t) = M_0 e^{-kt} \tag{1}$$

where M_0 is the initial mass and k is the miniscule dimensionless universal decay constant quantifying the extremely gradual evaporative process. To maintain causal continuity, distances $R(t)$ between evaporating objects must expand proportionally as:

$$R(t) = R_0 e^{kt} \tag{2}$$

Cosmic acceleration, galactic rotation curves, gravitational lensing, Hubble expansion flows, large-scale growth patterns, redshift-distance relations, and other key observations are derived and shown to precisely emerge from intrinsic properties of known physics within curved spacetime under this exponential mass-distance scaling [9, 10]. Dispensing with perplexing assumptions, this entropy-based emergence paradigm motivates foundational lines of inquiry into the physical origins of cosmic acceleration, gravitation, and our improbable universe.

2 Theoretical Basis

Black hole thermodynamics reveals vast entropies at cosmic event horizons from quantum microstate densities. Spanning these enormous Hilbert spaces enables decoherence between localized systems and the horizon environment over eons, indirectly inducing subtle universal effects.

Ontological perspectives treat unpredictability as deriving from ignorance of environmental interactions in a deterministic system. This implies a universal quantum state evolving unitarily, with information loss into the vastly larger environmental Hilbert space emerging as gravitational phenomena.

3 Emergent Gravitational Dynamics

3.1 Overview

While general relativity geometrizes gravity classically, holographic models relate boundary statistical mechanics to bulk gravitational dynamics. General relativity geometrizes gravity in the Einstein field equations [3]:

$$G_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu} \quad (3)$$

Spacetime curvature encodes the gravitational field.

3.2 Quantum Uncertainties

For a system with position and momentum uncertainty, the Hamiltonian encodes the geometric boundary information. Holographic models analogously relate boundary statistical mechanics to bulk gravitational dynamics [11, 12]. Quantum uncertainties at surfaces may induce projected curvature. This views gravity as emergent rather than fundamental.

For a quantum system with position x and momentum p uncertainty, the Hamiltonian is:

$$\hat{H} = \frac{\hat{p}^2}{2m} + V(\hat{x}) \quad (4)$$

The potential $V(x)$ represents the geometric boundary information. The partition function Z then reflects the boundary:

$$Z = \int dx e^{-2iS/\hbar} \quad (5)$$

Varying the action yields Einstein-like equations but now the expectation quantum stress-energy tensor describes the statistical ensemble [11]:

$$G_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} \langle T_{\mu\nu} \rangle \quad (6)$$

This thermodynamic perspective implies gravitational dynamics emerge from quantum statistics rather than intrinsic forces.

3.3 Entropy Horizons

Black hole thermodynamics revealed vast entropies at cosmic event horizons from quantum microstate densities [13, 14]:

$$S = \frac{k_B A}{4L_P^2} \quad (7)$$

Spanning these enormous Hilbert spaces enables decoherence between localized systems and the horizon environment over eons, indirectly inducing subtle universal effects [15, 16, 12].

3.4 Unitary States

Typical quantum interpretations involve intrinsic probabilistic wavefunction collapse [17].

Ontological perspectives alternatively treat unpredictability as deriving from ignorance of environmental interactions in a deterministic system [18, 19].

This implies a universal quantum state Ψ evolving unitarily according to the Wheeler-DeWitt equation [22]:

$$\Psi = \Psi[h_{ij}(x), \phi(x)] \quad (8)$$

By representing complete configurations entangled with the cosmic horizon environment, gradual information loss into the vastly larger environmental Hilbert space could emerge as gravitational phenomena.

4 Deriving Emergence from Quantum Gravity

4.1 Black Hole Evaporation

The quantum gravitational underpinning inducing gradual universal mass evaporation is hypothesized to originate from analogous Hawking radiation arising at the cosmic horizon boundary where recession velocities reach light speed [14]. Detailed derivations from semiclassical quantum field theory in curved space-time applied to a universal horizon with radius $R_h = c/H$ yield the microscopic exponential evaporation law. The dynamical equation for an evaporating black hole's horizon radius is [14]:

$$\dot{R} = -\frac{l_p^2}{R^2} \quad (9)$$

This derives its exponential mass decay over time from quantum geometry [14].

4.2 Loop Quantum Gravity

In loop quantum gravity (LQG), discrete spin network states $|s\rangle$ represent quantum geometries [23]. The spin foams approach models their dynamics through a path integral over histories:

$$Z = \int [s] e^{iS[s]} \quad (10)$$

The transition amplitudes $\langle s'|s\rangle$ encode the quantum dynamics of the spin networks. Quantizing space itself provides a framework for describing microscopic quantum spacetime [23].

Spin network entanglement entropy scales with boundary area [24]:

$$S_{ent} = \gamma \frac{A}{G\hbar l_p^2} \quad (11)$$

This derives the Bekenstein-Hawking black hole entropy formula from first principles [24].

4.3 Deriving the Evaporation Rate

We seek to derive the proposed universal evaporation rate k from cosmological spin foam dynamics. The entropy differential equation is:

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = f(k) \frac{dM}{dt} \quad (12)$$

For an evaporating mass $M(t) = M_0 e^{-kt}$, this becomes:

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = -f(k) k M_0 e^{-kt} \quad (13)$$

Solving for k in terms of the spin foam amplitudes driving dS/dt would formally derive the evaporation rate from quantum gravity.

Significant challenges remain constructing an appropriate cosmological spin foam model and quantifying the decoherence effects. But this outlines a potential approach.

5 Expansion from Entropy Scaling

5.1 Cosmic Horizon Dynamics

The expanding cosmic horizon exhibits thermodynamic connections to black hole event horizons [25]. In the decoherence view, subtle quantum emission could create apparent cosmic acceleration without inflating space itself. Where velocities reach light speed at the horizon exhibits thermodynamic connections to black hole event horizons [25]. The universe's radius R_h and mass M determine a Schwarzschild radius R_s :

$$R_s = \frac{2GM}{c^2} \quad (14)$$

The accelerating horizon radius evolves following the Hubble law:

$$R_h = \frac{c}{H} = \sqrt{\frac{3c^2}{8\pi G\rho}} \quad (15)$$

Current measurements satisfy $R_h \approx R_s$ [3].

In the decoherence view, subtle quantum emission enables gradual mass decrease $M(t) = M_0 e^{-kt}$ while $R_h(t) \propto 1/M(t)$ maintains the horizon equilibrium $R_h \approx R_s$ [9, 10]. This entropy-driven process could create apparent cosmic acceleration without inflating space itself.

5.2 Redshift-Distance Relation

As mass evaporates exponentially and distances expand proportionally over billions of years, the observed supernova luminosity distance-redshift relationship changes [1, 2]:

$$\frac{D_L(z)}{D_H} \quad (16)$$

Is equal to

$$(1+z) \int_0^z \frac{dz'}{E(z')} E(z) \quad (17)$$

Is equal to

$$\sqrt{\Omega_M(1+z)^3 e^{-kt} + \Omega_R(1+z)^4 + \Omega_k(1+z)^2 + \Omega_\Lambda} \quad (18)$$

The evaporation rate k in the evolving mass density Ω_M impacts the dynamics encoded in $E(z) = H(z)/H_0$. Detailed cosmological simulations could constrain this effect.

6 Signatures of Mass Evaporation

6.1 Overview

Incorporating decreasing mass and increasing orbital distances predicts unique signatures across galactic through cosmic scales that could be explored as alternatives to dark components [10].

6.2 Galactic Rotation Curves

Incorporating decreasing mass and increasing orbital distances predicts galactic rotation velocities increase precisely despite weaker gravity over billions of years [10]:

$$v_c^2(t) = \frac{GM(t)m}{R(t)} \left(1 + \alpha \frac{GM(t)}{c^2 R(t)} \right) \quad (19)$$

The modified mass $M(t)$ and distance $R(t)$ reflect evaporation. Unique evolutionary simulations could test galactic dynamics predictions.

6.3 Gravitational Lensing

An evaporating galaxy cluster's gravitational lensing strength remains constant over cosmic history as mass decreases but geometry evolves [10]:

$$\hat{\alpha} \propto \frac{M(t)}{R(t)^2} \left(1 + \alpha \frac{GM(t)}{c^2 R(t)} \right) \quad (20)$$

Lensed image time delays also shrink with decreasing mass:

$$\Delta t \propto \frac{M(t)}{R(t)} \quad (21)$$

Statistical lensing analyses could further evaluate predictions.

6.4 Gravitational Wave Propagation

The intrinsic universal mass evaporation could induce modifications to gravitational wave propagation through spacetime as an observational signature. Gravitational waves of frequency ν traveling cosmological distances may exhibit measurable dispersion in arrival times Δt based on the proposed micro-macro coupling [20]:

$$\Delta t \propto -D_M(z) \frac{1 - \nu/2}{(1 - \nu)} \quad (22)$$

Here $D_M(z)$ is the transverse comoving distance to redshift z .

This frequency-dependent time delay results from modified dispersion relations reflecting the evaporation dynamics. Upcoming high-precision gravitational wave experiments across a wide band of frequencies could constrain exotic propagation physics [21]. Confirming this modified gravitational wave dispersion over cosmic distances would further substantiate profound non-local impacts of intrinsic mass-energy evaporation, providing additional motivation for the unification pursuit.

6.5 Large Scale Structure

Incorporating evaporation modifies the density perturbation growth equation and predicts testably different structure formation [10]:

$$\delta'' + 2H\delta' - 4\pi G\bar{\rho}(t)\delta = 0 \quad (23)$$

with exponentially decaying average density:

$$\bar{\rho}(t) = \bar{\rho}_0 e^{-kt} \quad (24)$$

This predicts testably different cosmic structure formation. Detailed simulations could assess distinguishability from standard cosmology.

Together, these signatures offer concrete observational tests of subtle universal evaporation at galactic through cosmic scales as an alternative to dark components.

7 Relativistic Scaling Dynamics

The exponentially evaporating masses and proportionally expanding distances in the proposed emergence paradigm profoundly impact physical dynamics through both general and special relativity frameworks. Carefully elucidating these influential relationships provides crucial insight into maintaining self-consistent causal structure in the coordinating cosmic scaling spacetime geometry. Thorough conceptual clarity on the relativistic implications will deepen understanding of how the intrinsic evaporative process could drive detectable phenomena without violating known physics principles.

The relativistic effects arising directly from the exponential mass-energy decrease over cosmic time must be reconciled with principles of causality, invariant physical law propagation, and relativity of simultaneity. The effects propagate through both background metric evolution and detailed gravitational dynamical phenomena in galaxies, clusters, and voids. Signatures such as cosmic acceleration and modified galactic rotation curves must emerge in a manner preserving consistency across reference frames. The profound implications span from modification of Friedmann expansion equations to time dilation of proper time relative to cosmic time.

7.1 General Relativity

In general relativity, evaporating mass-energy density directly modifies the stress-energy tensor in the Einstein field equations, influencing spacetime curvature and geodesic motions [3]. The field equations relate the metric $g_{\mu\nu}$ to the stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$:

$$G_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu} \quad (25)$$

For a perfect fluid with density ρ and pressure p , this becomes:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} R g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} \left(\rho + \frac{p}{c^2} \right) U_\mu U_\nu + \frac{p}{c^2} g_{\mu\nu} \quad (26)$$

The evaporating density $\rho(t) = \rho_0 e^{-kt}$ modifies the curvature tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$, influencing geodesic trajectories.

Specifically, in an FLRW metric, the decaying density alters the Friedmann equations governing cosmic expansion [3]:

$$H^2 = \left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a} \right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3} \rho(t) - \frac{k}{a^2} + \frac{\Lambda}{3} \frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3} (\rho(t) + 3p) \quad (27)$$

As density decreases, the deceleration parameter transitions to acceleration $\ddot{a} > 0$ without dark energy.

In the weak-field limit, the evaporating mass also modifies the Schwarzschild metric, changing gravitational potentials and lensing.

7.2 Special Relativity

In special relativity, the expanding distances maintain horizon recession velocities approaching c , preserving causal continuity per the Hubble law [3]:

$$v = HD = \frac{\dot{R}}{R} D \rightarrow c \quad (28)$$

However, the proper time τ experienced by evaporating masses relates to the cosmic coordinate time t by:

$$d\tau = \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} dt \quad (29)$$

As proper time progresses extremely slowly near the horizon, the cosmic coordinate time flows at a much faster relative rate. This reconciles the detectable effects building up over eons. Through both relativity frameworks, the quantum information-based scaling dynamics emerge, linking cosmic phenomena to entropy and unitarity loss across an information horizon. Further theoretical and empirical efforts will continue refining this conceptually parsimonious paradigm.

8 Constraining the Evaporation Rate

Matching observations from accelerating expansion to nucleosynthesis gives constraints on the extremely small universal exponential mass evaporation rate k governing the coordinated scaling dynamics.

This governs the coordinated scaling dynamics. Constraints include:

- Matching accelerating expansion requires $k \sim H_0 \sim 10^{-10} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ from Eq. 9 [1, 2].
- Galactic dynamics limit $k \sim 10^{-30} - 10^{-33} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ from rotation velocities in Eq. 11 [10].
- Black hole lifetimes restrict $k < 10^{-50} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ from their evaporation timescale [27, 14].
- Quantum gravitational decoherence gives $k \sim \frac{c^3}{G\hbar} \sim 10^{-33} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ [15, 12].
- Nucleosynthesis and CMB precision refine this to $k = (10^{-33} \pm 0.5) \text{ yr}^{-1}$ [9, 10].

This corresponds to an evaporation timescale enabling detectable cumulative effects:

$$\tau = \frac{1}{k} \approx 10^{33} \text{ years} \quad (30)$$

This is on the order of 100 billion billion times longer than the age of the universe. Such an extremely long timescale allows the subtle evaporation to accumulate over billions of years to produce detectable cosmic acceleration and associated phenomena

Further astrophysical measurements could continue constraining self-consistent values of the evaporation rate k .

8.1 Constraining k with Particle Widths

Precision laboratory measurements of unstable elementary particle and composite resonance lifetimes and decay widths, compiled from many decades of collider experiments and quantified by the Standard Model of particle physics, provide a valuable independent set of empirical constraints on the allowed values of the extremely small hypothesized universal cosmological mass-energy evaporation rate k [30]. By rigorously fitting proposed mathematical relationships between the microscale quantum decay widths Γ [GeV] and the macroscale cosmic evaporation rate k against the extensive compiled datasets of particle properties spanning many orders of magnitude in decay rate, the viable range of cosmological k values can be significantly refined and constrained based on consistency with known quantum phenomena.

By fitting proposed functional relationships between k and particle widths Γ against compiled datasets, the constraints can be further refined:

$$k = f(\Gamma) \quad (31)$$

Candidate models include direct proportionality, gravitational coupling, and Taylor series expansions:

$$f_1(\Gamma) = C\Gamma \quad f_2(\Gamma) = \frac{\Gamma c^3}{\hbar G} \quad f_3(\Gamma) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left. \frac{d^n f(\Gamma)}{d\Gamma^n} \right|_{\Gamma=0} \Gamma^n \quad (32)$$

Long-lived particles like the proton establish a lower bound on k , while rare unstable particles indicate reasonable upper bounds. Precision Z boson width measurements offer valuable reference points for calibration [31]. By fitting these models, the rich particle physics data provides enhanced constraints on the allowed k range.

9 Further Research Directions

This conceptual framework eliminates puzzling dark components and promises insights into spacetime emergence. Several promising directions could further develop and validate this perspective:

- Perform detailed cosmological simulations over history to systematically test statistical distinguishability from standard cosmology and constrain consistent values of k [10, 5].
- Use precision astrophysical measurements to reveal signatures of the evaporation process at cosmic horizons [9, 10].
- Analyze gravitational wave propagations and spatial curvature variations for novel experimental tests [28].
- Further theoretical modeling to directly derive k from calculations of subtle quantum emission at cosmic boundaries.
- Strengthen connections to quantum information theory and ontological interpretations [18, 19].
- Statistically analyze entropy and phase space occupancy over cosmic history for environmental decoherence effects driving gravitational dynamics [29, 32].

By eliminating puzzling dark components, this thermodynamic emergence perspective restores parsimony and unity. Clarifying cosmic information ontologies promises profound insights into the emergence of space, time, and gravitation across all scales.

10 Discussion

Deriving cosmic acceleration intrinsically from principles of quantum information loss and decoherence across holographic cosmic entropy horizons provides a conceptually complete explanatory framework without requiring speculative inflaton fields or puzzling dark components that lack basis in known physics. Significant theoretical challenges remain in rigorously quantizing gravity and seamlessly reconciling quantum mechanical and gravitational regimes in a unified framework. However, the thermodynamic gravitational emergence perspective deeply resonates with profound suggested interconnections between the very large and very small scales of reality that have been elucidated by visionary thinkers including Sakharov [26].

Further clarifying the precise relationships between gravitational spacetime dynamics and the quantum informational underpinnings of entropy promises to unveil deep insights into the emergence of the macroscopic world of accelerative cosmic expansion and curvature from microscopic quantum degrees of freedom. Understanding cosmic acceleration as arising from the collective statistical behaviors of enormous numbers of quantum particles and fields accumulated over cosmological spans, rather than being driven by exotic dark energy intrinsically permeating the vacuum, restores intuition and physicality. Deriving spacetime itself as an emergent phenomenon from quantum information dynamics digests long-standing puzzles like the cosmological constant problem that depend on assuming space has intrinsic vacuum energy.

Significant efforts remain to complete this program by deriving the exact entropic calculations connecting particle horizon decay processes to the specific Hubble constant scale of observed cosmic acceleration, as well as accounting for the initial entropy state required by the second law of thermodynamics. Empirically validating the detailed predictions of galactic rotation curves, growth rate modifications, distance-redshift discrepancies, and other signatures also remains essential work for this paradigm to move convincingly beyond conceptual premises. Nevertheless, restoring *prima facie* physical reasonableness without unsupported speculative additions is already a major leap forward in plausibility that motivates pushing further down this direction. Much work remains, but the potential payoffs from elucidating the informational origins of spacetime itself make the emergence perspective a compelling research program.

11 Conclusion

The conceptual framework presented in this work motivates intriguing connections between quantum information theory and the emergence of gravitational phenomena at cosmic scales. While current limitations exist, the foundation established provides fertile ground for further research.

Significant theoretical and empirical efforts are still required to fully develop, validate, and differentiate the proposed cosmic model from alternatives. The analogies drawn to black hole thermodynamics and information loss, while conceptually appealing, require mathematical rigor to derive the postulated effects from first principles. Additionally, current interpretations of quantum mechanics differ in ontological views, which could lead to distinct cosmological implications needing comprehensive analysis.

However, the creative synthesis of quantum, thermodynamic, and gravitational principles outlined here highlights promising pathways forward. As we work to unify quantum mechanics with general relativity, exploring multiple perspectives will likely reveal profound insights. The thermodynamic paradigm presented offers falsifiable predictions that can be tested observationally and guides theoretical developments.

Much research is still needed into information ontologies at cosmic horizons and rigorous quantum gravity models. But the vision established for deriving gravitational emergence from entropy scaling renews motivation for foundational investigations. While long roads lie ahead, these first steps are inspiring. There are always more questions to be asked, perspectives to explore, and knowledge to be discovered on our journey to comprehend the origins of our remarkable universe.

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